

Welfare Package Disparities, Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Organisational Dynamics: Evidence from Public Schools in Oyo East Local Government, Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose: This study examined the impact of disparities in welfare packages among different categories of teachers on job satisfaction, morale, and teamwork in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria, with particular attention to equity concerns in teacher welfare distribution.

Methodology: Grounded in Equity Theory (Adams, 1965) and Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), the study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A sample of 225 teachers was selected through stratified random sampling from primary and secondary schools. Data were collected using structured questionnaires validated by educational research experts (Cronbach's alpha = 0.82). Descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis were employed at the 0.05 significance level.

Findings: Results showed that 74.7% of teachers believed welfare package disparities influence overall job satisfaction, with 40.9% indicating significant influence. Regression analysis demonstrated that disparities significantly predicted job satisfaction (beta = 0.708, $p < .001$), explaining 58.4% of variance ($R^2 = .584$). A substantial majority of 78.7% of teachers reported that disparities significantly affect overall morale and teamwork, with only 4.0% reporting no discernible impact.

Practical Implications: Perceived inequity in welfare distribution substantially undermines teacher satisfaction and organisational cohesion, requiring equitable welfare policies and transparent implementation mechanisms.

Originality/Value: This study provides an early empirical examination of welfare disparity impacts on both individual satisfaction and organisational dynamics in a Nigerian local government context, demonstrating that distributional equity matters as much as absolute welfare levels.

Keywords:

welfare disparities, teacher categories, job satisfaction, organisational morale, teamwork, equity theory, Nigeria

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Educational systems worldwide confront persistent challenges in ensuring equitable treatment of teachers across employment categories and experience levels. In Nigeria, the level of job satisfaction among teachers has emerged as a subject of substantial concern given its demonstrable influence on educational quality (Adeniyi & Olasehinde, 2022; Oyewole et al., 2021). Disparities in welfare provisions among permanent, contract, and part-time teachers have been documented across multiple states (Abolade & Adeyemi, 2021; Aderinto & Ogunsola, 2021; Oladapo & Ogunyemi, 2022), raising fundamental questions about their consequences for teacher satisfaction and school-level organisational functioning. These disparities manifest in unequal salary scales, healthcare benefits, housing allowances, professional development opportunities, and retirement benefits across teacher categories. Recent evidence from Nigerian public schools confirms that working conditions and fringe benefits, when perceived as inequitably distributed, significantly undermine teacher job performance and morale (Nwakaego et al., 2024; Agah & Yakubu, 2024).

While some variation in welfare packages may be justified by experience, qualifications, or employment terms, the perceived fairness of such variation significantly influences teacher attitudes and behaviours (Adams, 1965). Teachers who perceive unfair disparities tend to report reduced satisfaction, diminished

organisational commitment, and elevated turnover intentions (Iabor & Okolie, 2019; Mitchell et al., 2001). Beyond individual responses, perceived inequity may erode collective organisational dynamics by reducing morale, impairing teamwork, and weakening the collaborative cultures essential for school effectiveness (Ebo & Oredein, 2021). Recent empirical evidence confirms that distributional fairness in compensation functions as a central predictor of teacher satisfaction, often exceeding the influence of absolute salary levels (Agbakwuru & Iyawe, 2023; Annamalai, 2022; Glaveli et al., 2024).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite theoretical and policy relevance, empirical research has not systematically examined how welfare disparities specifically affect both individual satisfaction and collective organisational dynamics in Nigerian local government education contexts. Most existing studies either document the existence of disparities without measuring their impacts, focus narrowly on individual satisfaction while neglecting morale and teamwork effects, or operate at state level without attending to local government implementation realities. Without systematic evidence, policymakers lack the data required to address potential inequity and its organisational consequences.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The primary purpose was to examine the impact of welfare package disparities among different teacher categories on job satisfaction and organisational dynamics in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specific objectives were to: (i) determine teachers' perceptions of whether welfare disparities influence job satisfaction; (ii) compare the perceived impact of senior versus junior teacher welfare packages on satisfaction; (iii) assess the extent to which disparities affect overall morale and teamwork; and (iv) examine the predictive relationship between disparities and job satisfaction.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant impact of disparities in welfare packages among different categories of teachers on their respective job satisfaction levels.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Welfare Disparities in Education

A welfare package refers to the combination of benefits and services that an organisation provides to its employees to enhance their wellbeing, performance, and job satisfaction (Cannas et al., 2019). In educational contexts, welfare packages typically include salary, health insurance, housing, transportation, bonuses, and professional development opportunities. Welfare disparities refer specifically to differences in these benefits across employment categories within the same system (Abolade & Adeyemi, 2021). These disparities may be formally sanctioned by policy frameworks or emerge informally through inconsistent implementation, and their perceived legitimacy determines whether they generate inequity distress or are accepted as reasonable differentiation (Adams, 1965).

2.1.2 Organisational Dynamics: Morale and Teamwork

Morale refers to the collective psychological state of employees regarding their work environment, characterised by enthusiasm, confidence, and willingness to cooperate (Eke, 2018). High morale reflects positive attitudes toward work, colleagues, and the organisation, while low morale manifests as disengagement, negativity, and reduced effort. In school settings, teacher morale significantly influences classroom climate, instructional quality, and student outcomes. Teamwork involves collaborative effort toward shared educational goals, requiring trust, communication, and mutual support (Salancik & Pfeffer, 1977). Welfare disparities may undermine both dimensions by creating perceived inequity, generating resentment, and eroding the collaborative norms essential for effective schools.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Equity Theory

Adams' (1965) Equity Theory holds that employees compare their input-outcome ratios with those of referent others. Inputs include effort, skills, experience, and qualifications; outcomes include pay, benefits, recognition, and status. When these ratios are perceived as unequal, tension arises that individuals seek to reduce by altering inputs, pursuing outcome

changes, or leaving the situation. Agbakwuru and Iyawe (2023) confirmed in a Nigerian university context that a moderately positive relationship exists between employee welfare and job satisfaction, establishing that improvements in welfare distribution produce corresponding gains in satisfaction. Annamalai (2022) confirmed that perceived equity was a significant direct predictor of job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.43$, $p < .001$) in Indian higher education.

2.2.2 Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory (Homans, 1958; Blau, 1964) frames employment as an exchange governed by norms of reciprocity. Employees contribute effort, commitment, and loyalty in exchange for compensation, benefits, recognition, and security. Rokeman et al. (2023) confirmed that reward systems function through exchange dynamics: teachers who perceive their reward structure as fair and commensurate with their contribution report higher satisfaction and stronger job performance orientation. Ozgenel et al. (2022) demonstrated that organisational justice, functioning through social exchange processes, strongly mediates the relationship between leadership and teacher job satisfaction in Turkish public schools.

2.2.3 Job Embeddedness Theory

Mitchell et al. (2001) proposed that job embeddedness-comprising fit with organisation and community, links to colleagues, and sacrifice involved in leaving - predicts retention beyond satisfaction and commitment. Welfare disparities may weaken embeddedness by reducing perceived fit with an inequitable organisation and damaging collegial links through status resentment. Opoku et al. (2025), working across Ethiopia and Malawi, found that teacher category and place of teaching significantly moderated the relationship between retention and job satisfaction, confirming that embeddedness operates differently across teacher sub-groups because their welfare-related experiences differ.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Nigerian Studies on Welfare and Teacher Satisfaction

Within Oyo State, Olaleye and Abiodun

(2020) documented a positive relationship between welfare packages and job satisfaction among public secondary school teachers, establishing that salary, health benefits, housing, and professional development each contribute to teacher satisfaction. Abolade and Adeyemi (2021) found significant relationships between welfare variation and satisfaction across categories, with perceived fairness of distribution predicting satisfaction beyond absolute package levels. Oladapo and Ogunyemi (2022) documented significant satisfaction differences favouring permanent over non-permanent teachers. Ibikunle et al. (2021) found that a significant proportion of teachers experienced psychological distress, with satisfaction scores negatively correlated with the General Health Questionnaire, confirming that satisfaction deficits carry wellbeing consequences. Nwakaego et al. (2024) found that working conditions and fringe benefits significantly influenced teacher job performance in Cross River State, and Agah and Yakubu (2024) confirmed that fringe benefits and staff development significantly predicted teacher performance in Adamawa State.

2.3.2 International Evidence on Welfare, Reward, and Teacher Satisfaction

Glaveli et al. (2024) examined the determinants of teacher job satisfaction in 438 Greek primary schools using Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis and found that all examined facets of the work environment, including self-fulfilment opportunities, work intensity, salary, leadership, and collegial relations, were essential to job satisfaction, with salary identified as a potential future threat if not adequately addressed. Rokeman et al. (2023) reviewed reward and teacher satisfaction across multiple studies, concluding that reward structures, both financial and non-financial, are central determinants of satisfaction and that their perceived fairness matters as much as their absolute level. Opoku et al. (2025) conducted a cross-national study of teacher retention and job satisfaction in Ethiopia and Malawi, finding that teacher type and place of teaching significantly moderated the relationship between retention and satisfaction, confirming that satisfaction outcomes are not uniform across teacher sub-groups.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, appropriate for examining perceptions and their associations across a defined population (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This design enabled the collection of standardised data from a representative sample of teachers while preserving the contextual integrity of welfare experiences in Oyo East Local Government. A similar design was adopted in comparable Nigerian welfare studies (Nwakaego et al., 2024; Agah & Yakubu, 2024).

3.2 Population, Sampling, and Sample Size

The target population comprised all teachers in Oyo East Local Government's 23 public primary schools and 9 public secondary schools. Using stratified random sampling based on school level, 10 primary schools and 5 secondary schools were selected. All consenting teachers in the selected schools participated, yielding a final sample of 225 respondents. Demographic characteristics showed that 45.3% were male and 54.7% female, with the majority (57.8%) having between 6 and 10 years of teaching experience, and 65.3% holding a first degree qualification.

3.3 Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire comprised five sections: Section A collected demographic characteristics (8 items); Section B elicited perceptions of welfare disparity influence on satisfaction; Section C examined comparative perceptions of senior versus junior teacher packages; Section D assessed disparity effects on morale and teamwork; and Section E administered a 10-item welfare disparity assessment scale rated on a 4-point Likert format. Three educational research experts A combined 74.7% of teachers (40.9% significantly; 33.8% to some extent) believed that welfare package disparities influence job satisfaction. Only 10.2% reported no significant influence, while 15.1% were uncertain.

validated the instrument for content and face validity. Reliability testing with 30 teachers drawn from outside the main sample yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82 for the disparity assessment scale, exceeding the 0.70 threshold recommended by Nunnally (1978).

3.4 Data Collection and Analysis

Questionnaires were administered personally to participants in selected schools across two weeks. Completed instruments were retrieved immediately upon completion to maximise return rates. Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) addressed Research Questions 1 to 3. Simple linear regression analysis tested the null hypothesis and addressed Research Question 4 at the 0.05 significance level.

4. Results

4.1 Research Question 1: Do Welfare Disparities Influence Job Satisfaction?

Table 1 presents teachers' perceptions of whether welfare package disparities influence overall job satisfaction.

Table 1. Perceived Influence of Welfare Disparities on Job Satisfaction

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes, significantly	92	40.9
Yes, to some extent	76	33.8
No, not significantly	23	10.2
I am not sure	34	15.1
Total	225	100.0

4.2 Research Question 2: Senior versus Junior Teacher Package Comparisons

Table 2 presents teachers' perceptions of the comparative impact of senior and junior teacher welfare packages on job satisfaction.

Table 2. Comparative Impact of Senior versus Junior Teacher Welfare Packages

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Both packages impact satisfaction equally	93	41.3
Senior teachers' package significantly impacts satisfaction	57	25.3
Junior teachers' package significantly impacts satisfaction	44	19.6
No significant difference observed	31	13.8
Total	225	100.0

The largest proportion (41.3%) believed both packages affect satisfaction equally. A quarter (25.3%) emphasised senior teachers' packages, while 19.6% emphasised junior teachers' packages. A minority (13.8%) observed no significant difference.

4.3. Research Question 3: Impact on Morale and Teamwork

Table 3 presents the reported extent to which welfare disparities affect overall teacher morale and teamwork.

Table 3. Effect of Welfare Disparities on Morale and Teamwork

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Significantly impacts Morale and teamwork	177	78.7
Somewhat impacts morale and teamwork	22	9.8
Minor impact on morale and teamwork	17	7.6
No discernible impact	9	4.0
Total	225	100.0

A substantial majority (78.7%) reported that disparities significantly affect morale and teamwork. Combined with those reporting some impact (9.8%), 88.5% perceived at least a partial effect on organisational dynamics. Only 4.0% reported no discernible impact.

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant impact of welfare package disparities on teacher job satisfaction.

Tables 4 and 5 present the regression model summary and coefficients respectively.

Table 4. Regression Model Summary (Disparities Predicting Job Satisfaction)

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	Sig.
1	.628	.584	.580	50.142	.000

Table 5. Regression Coefficients

Variable	B (Unstd.)	Std. Error	Beta (Std.)	t	p
Constant	.392	.227	--	1.728	.085
Disparities	.708	.100	.428	7.081	.000

Note. Dependent variable: Job Satisfaction. Predictor: Disparities in Welfare Packages. Welfare disparities significantly predicted job satisfaction (beta = .708, t = 7.081, p < .001), accounting for 58.4% of the variance in job satisfaction (RZ = .584). The null hypothesis was rejected at the 0.05 significance level.

5. Discussion

5.1 Perception of Disparity Influence on Job Satisfaction

The finding that 74.7% of teachers perceived welfare disparities as influencing job satisfaction strongly supports Equity Theory (Adams, 1965). Teachers do not evaluate welfare in absolute terms alone; they actively compare their packages with those of colleagues in other categories, and perceived disparities generate inequity distress that shapes satisfaction independently of actual package adequacy. This result aligns with Abolade and Adeyemi (2021) and Olaleye and Abiodun (2020), who documented positive relationships between welfare provisions and teacher satisfaction in Oyo State. The result is consistent with Agbakwuru and Iyawe (2023), who confirmed in a Nigerian university context that employee welfare improvements corresponded with satisfaction gains, and with Annamalai (2022), who demonstrated that perceived equity directly predicted educator satisfaction (beta = 0.43, p < .001).

5.2 Senior versus Junior Teacher Package Comparisons

The finding that 41.3% of teachers believed both senior and junior packages affect satisfaction equally reflects recognition that welfare equity concerns are not confined to any single employment category. The divergent emphases observed, with 25.3% prioritising senior packages and 19.6% prioritising junior packages, are consistent with Social Information Processing Theory (Salancik & Pfeffer, 1977). Oyewole et al. (2021) found that salary and remuneration were among the primary satisfaction factors for public secondary school teachers in Oyo State. Rokeman et al. (2023) established that reward structures carry differential salience depending on a teacher's position in the occupational hierarchy, supporting the pattern of category-based divergence observed in this study.

5.3 Impact on Morale and Teamwork

The finding that 78.7% of teachers reported disparities significantly affecting morale and teamwork demonstrates that welfare disparities generate organisational costs extending beyond individual dissatisfaction. Equity-based resentment appears to manifest as reduced enthusiasm, interpersonal tension, and reluctance to cooperate across category lines, consistent with Eke's (2018) conceptualisation of morale and with Ebo and Oredein's (2021) analysis of commitment and organisational functioning among Oyo State teachers. Werang et al. (2017) confirmed in Indonesian elementary schools that teacher job satisfaction positively influenced organisational commitment, reinforcing the proposition that satisfaction deficits driven by perceived inequity have collective as well as individual consequences.

5.4 Predictive Relationship between Disparities and Job Satisfaction

The regression finding that welfare disparities predicted job satisfaction ($\beta = .708$, $RZ = .584$, $p < .001$) indicates a strong and statistically significant relationship. The explained variance of 58.4% substantially exceeds typical effect sizes in organisational research. Glaveli et al. (2024) demonstrated that salary and collegial relations were among the most consequential determinants of primary school teacher satisfaction, supporting the proposition that compensation-related equity functions as a

structural rather than peripheral satisfaction driver. This implication is consistent with Adams' (1965) Equity Theory and Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964): welfare reform strategies that increase total expenditure without attending to distributional equity are unlikely to produce sustainable satisfaction improvements

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

This study concludes that welfare package disparities among different teacher categories significantly influence job satisfaction and substantially affect organisational morale and teamwork in Oyo East Local Government. A majority of 74.7% of teachers perceived disparities as influencing satisfaction, with 40.9% indicating significant influence. Disparities strongly predicted job satisfaction ($\beta = .708$, $RZ = .584$, $p < .001$). Critically, 78.7% reported that disparities significantly affect morale and teamwork, demonstrating that inequity extends beyond individual satisfaction to collective organisational dynamics. These findings establish that perceived fairness in welfare distribution is as consequential for teacher outcomes as the absolute level of welfare provision.

6.2 Recommendations

For Oyo State Government: Conduct a comprehensive equity audit of teacher welfare packages across all employment categories to identify unjustified disparities. Develop standardised frameworks specifying legitimate bases for variation while eliminating arbitrary differentials. Implement transparent distribution mechanisms with clear communication of criteria, and establish accessible grievance channels for teachers perceiving inequitable treatment.

For Oyo East Local Government Education Authority: Conduct local equity assessments identifying category-specific disparities. Ensure consistent implementation of state welfare policies across all schools, provide administrator training on equitable welfare distribution, and monitor morale and teamwork indicators as early warning signals of emerging inequity perceptions.

For Future Research: Comparative studies examining disparity impacts across Nigerian states and local governments are needed.

Qualitative investigations of mechanisms linking disparities to morale and teamwork would deepen understanding. Longitudinal designs examining whether equity improvements translate into sustained satisfaction gains are also warranted.

References

- Abolade, A. O., & Adeyemi, T. O. (2021). Variations in welfare package and job satisfaction among teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(12), 1–10.
- Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequity in social exchange. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 2, pp. 267–299). Academic Press.
- Aderinto, A. A., & Ogunsola, O. A. (2021). Effects of welfare package variations on job satisfaction of teachers in Oyo State. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 9(2), 8–18.
- Adeniyi, O. F., & Olasehinde, O. I. (2022). Job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 9(2), 138–149.
- Agah, P. M., & Yakubu, N. (2024). Impact of conditions of service on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Gombi Education Zone, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(2), 2236–2246.
<https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.802159>
- Agbakwuru, K. N., & Iyawe, B. O. (2023). Employee welfare and job satisfaction among non-academic staff of universities in Ekiti State. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 18(1), 44–52.
<https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.1.0537>
- Annamalai, S. (2022). Influence of perceived equity, job enrichment, and burnout among educators in Indian private universities on job satisfaction and the desire to quit. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, 991068.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.991068>
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. Wiley.
- Cannas, M., Bruno, S. S., Sironi, E., & Mentel, U. (2019). Job satisfaction and subjective well-being in Europe. *Economics and Sociology*, 12(4), 183–196.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE.
- Ebo, A. A., & Oredein, A. O. (2021). Job and organisational commitment of public secondary school teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Ife Social Sciences Review*, 29(2), 43–52.
- Eke, G. J. (2018). Contemporary issues in employee motivation and performance in organisations. *Social Sciences*, 5(1), 45–58.
- Glaveli, N., Manolitzas, P., Tsourou, E., & Grigoroudis, E. (2024). Unlocking teacher job satisfaction during the COVID-19 pandemic: A multi-criteria satisfaction analysis. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(1), 1264–1285.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01124-z>
- Homans, G. C. (1958). Social behaviour as exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597–606.
- Ibikunle, M. A., Afolabi, R. F., & Bello, S. (2021). Job satisfaction and psychological distress among teachers in selected schools in Ibadan, Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Occupational Health and Epidemiology*, 10(4), 266–273.
- Irabor, I. E., & Okolie, U. C. (2019). A review of employees' job satisfaction and its effect on their retention. *Annals of Spiru Haret University, Economic Series*, 19(2), 93–114.
- Mitchell, T. R., Holtom, B. C., Lee, T. W., Sablinski, C. J., & Erez, M. (2001). Why people stay: Using job embeddedness to predict voluntary turnover. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44(6), 1102–1121.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Nwakaego, C. E., Obona, E. E., & Andeshi, W. A. (2024). Impact of working conditions and fringe benefits on job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Education*, 7(2), 344–360.
- Oladapo, O. E., & Ogunyemi, F. O. (2022). Comparative study of job satisfaction among permanent and non-permanent teachers in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 13(1), 1–11.
- Olaleye, F. O., & Abiodun, A. J. (2020). Teachers' welfare packages and job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(17), 53–62.
- Opoku, M. P., Nketsia, W., Belbase, S., Side, A. S., Jiya, A. N., & Gameda, F. T. (2025). A cross-national study of teacher retention and

job satisfaction in Sub-Saharan Africa. Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth, 69(2), 137–148.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1045988X.2024.2361874>

Oyewole, O. B., Ayodele, K. O., & Ayeni, A. O. (2021). Factors influencing job satisfaction among public secondary school teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews*, 11(1), 39–47.

Ozgenel, M., Yazici, S., & Asmaz, A. (2022). The mediator role of organisational justice in the relationship between school principals' agile leadership characteristics and teachers' job

satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 895540.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.895540>

Rokeman, N. R. M., Kob, C. G. C., & Sobry, H. C. (2023). The role of reward in teachers' job satisfaction towards job performance: A literature review. *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 8(11), e002591. <https://doi.org/10.47405/mjssh.v8i11.2591>

Salancik, G. R., & Pfeffer, J. (1977). An examination of need-satisfaction models of job attitudes.

Administrative Science Quarterly, 22(3), 427–456.

Werang, B. R., Agung, A. A. G., & Agung, G. (2017). Teachers' job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and performance in Indonesia. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 6(8), 700–711.